

Separation of Powers in Indian Perspective

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Abstract

The Doctrine of Separation of Powers seeks to protect the centralization of power in one hand; as history has repeatedly demonstrated centralisation of power in one or a few hands can lead to disastrous outcomes. The application of this principle makes the government liable, accountable, and answerable to its citizens for its actions, thereby aiding in the promotion and protection of human rights. For the smooth functioning of any government, cooperation and coordination among all three wings of the government is necessary. After considering all the aspects of separation of power, it needs to be remembered that complete separation of power is possible neither in theory nor in practice. Indian Constitution had not indeed recognized the doctrine of separation of powers in its absolute rigidity but the functions of different parts or branches of the Government have been sufficiently differentiated. If the legislature or the executive is not functioning properly it is for the people to correct the defects by exercising their franchise properly in the next elections and voting for candidates who will fulfil their expectations, or by other lawful methods like peaceful demonstrations. The remedy is not in the judiciary taking over the legislative or executive functions, because that will not only violate the delicate balance of power enshrined in the Constitution, but also harm the institution of judiciary as it neither has the expertise nor the resources to perform those functions.

Keywords: Separation of Powers, India and Indian Constitution.

Introduction

Separation of Powers means the distribution of powers among organs of the state to perform their functions without any interference from other organs. The Separation of Powers as a doctrine of Governance in modern states has a limited application as we can't put the organs of state in water-tight compartments and expect them to work effectively.

The Doctrine of Separation of Powers seeks to protect the centralization of power in one hand; as history has repeatedly demonstrated, centralisation of power in one or a few hands can lead to disastrous outcomes. The application of this principle makes the government liable, accountable, and answerable to its citizens for its actions, thereby aiding in the promotion and protection of human rights. This eliminates one of the most serious weaknesses of other forms of administration, such as monarchy or dictatorship, in which the king is not accountable to his people. This assures that the laws are just, fair, and adhere to the natural justice ideal. Furthermore, because it is independent of the other departments, the court can administer equitable justice. Democracy is flawed without Separation of Power.

India follows constitutional democracy which offers a clear separation of powers. However, what India practices may be better called separation of functions and not powers. In India, the Judiciary is independent of the other two branches with the power to interpret the constitution. Parliament has the legislative powers. Executive powers are vested in the President who is advised by the Union Council of Ministers headed by the Prime Minister.

Origin

The term "trias politica" or "separation of powers" was coined by Montesquieu, an 18th century French social and political philosopher, although the English philosopher John Locke had earlier argued that legislative power

should be divided between king and Parliament. Montesquieu's publication, Spirit of the Laws, is considered one of the great works in the history of political theory and jurisprudence, which inspired the French Declaration of the Rights of Man and the Constitution of the United States. Under his model, the political authority of the state is divided into legislative, executive and judicial powers. He asserted that, to most effectively promote liberty, these three powers must be separate and acting independently. Separation of powers, therefore, refers to the division of government responsibilities into distinct branches to limit any one branch from exercising the core functions of another.

Montesquieu went on to clarify the idea in his own words:

“When the legislative and executive powers are united in the same person, or in the same body of magistrates, there can be no liberty. Again, there is no liberty if the judicial power is not separated from the legislative and executive powers. Were it joined with the legislative, the life and liberty of the subject would be exposed to arbitrary control, for the Judge would then be the legislator. Were it joined with the executive power, the Judge might behave with violence and oppression.

There would be an end of everything, were the same man or same body, whether of the nobles or of the people, to exercise those three powers, that of enacting laws, that of executing the public resolutions, and that of judging the crimes or differences of individuals.”

Meaning

Separation of powers divides the mechanism of governance into three branches i.e. Legislature, Executive and the Judiciary. According to Wade and Phillips, it may mean three different things:

1. Each organ should have different persons in capacity, i.e., a person with a function in one organ should not be a part of another organ.
2. One organ should not interfere in the functioning of the other organs.
3. One organ should not exercise the functions of another organ (they should stick to their mandate only).

Constituent Assembly Debates

There are two most notable thread of discussions in the Constituent Assembly regarding the Separation of Powers Doctrine when it was discussed and debated in the esteemed house on the proposals moved by Prof. K.T. Shah.

A. Separation of Powers

On 10th December, 1948, Prof. K.T. Shah moved a proposal to insert a new article 40-A, which emphasized upon the separation of powers which read, ‘40-A. *There shall be complete separation of powers as between the principal organs of the State, viz, the Legislative, the Executive, and the Judicial.*’

Shri K. Hanumanthaiya dissented with the proposed article and said that the constitutional structure which the assembly has approved is parliamentary government but the amendment of Prof. Shah seems to sponsor Presidential Executive. He further commented : “*Instead of having a conflicting trinity it is better to have a harmonious governmental structure. If we completely separate the executive, judiciary and the legislature conflicts are bound to arise between these three departments of Government. In any country or in any government, conflicts are suicidal to the peace and progress of the country..... Therefore in a governmental structure it is necessary to have what is called “harmony” and not this three-fold conflict.*”

Prof. Shibban Lal Saksena also agreed with the view of Shri K. Hanumanthaiya and remarked :

I know that in England they are working the system in a perfect manner. But they have a tradition of 700 years. They have developed their methods whereas we are just entering upon our democratic freedom and we cannot imitate it to perfection. It will have to wait until the whole national character changes and it is not possible that

we can imitate England. Probably, our slavery has led us to imitate the British system. If left to ourselves we would have copied the American system. In that system there is complete separation of the judicature from the legislature and the legislature from the executive. The legislature there can pass any laws which it thinks best for the country and the President has to obey them. Here the Leader of the majority party must have the House with him. The House will only pass those laws which the party thinks are necessary. The legislature cannot be independent of, but it has to be submissive to, the executive.....I, however, think that now we have gone too far to change the basis of our Constitution, because in the last two years we have passed everything in accordance with the British Constitution, and probably it is too late now in the day to change the whole system.

Kazi Syed Karimuddin made an agreement with the amendment of Prof. K. T. Shah and commented “*I know that the system approved by the Constituent Assembly is a Parliamentary system of government but even then I had urged the adoption of a non-parliamentary system of government in India.We have seen that the Ministers are slaves of the legislature and they have to depend for their existence and for their continuance in office on the popular views of the people in the country. They cannot use their independent judgment; they cannot use their independent discretion; the result is that those who keep them in power influence the judgment and the discretion of the Ministers to the great detriment of those who are in opposition.*”

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, one of the important architect of Indian Constitution, disagreeing with the argument of Prof. K.T. Shah, advocated thus: “There is no dispute whatsoever that the executive should be separated from the judiciary. With regard to the separation of the executive from the legislature, it is true that such a separation does exist in the Constitution of United States; but many Americans themselves were quite dissatisfied with the rigid separation embodied in the American Constitution between the executive and legislature..... There is not slightest doubt in my mind and in the minds of many students of Political Science, that the work of Parliament is so complicated, so vast that unless and until the members of the Legislature receive direct guidance and initiative from the members of the Executive, sitting in Parliament, it would be very difficult for Members of Parliament to carry on the work of the Legislature.

With the aforesaid observations, the motion initiated by Prof. Shah was turned down.

B. Independence of Judiciary

Thereafter, on 23rd May, 1949, Prof. Shah proposed a new article in motion emphasizing on the independence of Judiciary from other organs which read: “*102-A. Subject to this constitution the Judiciary in India shall be completely separate from the wholly independent of the Executive or the Legislature.*”

Opposing the motion, Shri K.M.Munshi remarked:

“the last 150 years of experience has shown that the doctrine of separation of powers cannot be maintained in a modern State. Today we find the Executive appointing numbers of tribunals of a quasi-judicial character. We find a large number of rules made by the Executive under law regulating conduct of different kinds. In modern State, the Executive enjoys certain powers of legislation as well as of deciding disputes. We also find Industrial courts which are taking upon themselves the right to adjudicate upon rights between the parties. On the other hand we find that the Judiciary has sometimes to perform functions which may be Executive in a very narrow sense. Therefore the doctrine of separation of powers is an exploded doctrine. This Constitution has been based on an entirely different principle, adopting the British model. We have invested the Judiciary with as much independence as is possessed by the Privy Council in England and to a large extent, by the Supreme Court of America; but any water-tight compartments of powers have been rejected.

While supporting the new article, R. K. Sidhva said :

“*The prosecutor and the Judge should not be the same person and that is what is at present existing in this country and there has been miscarriage of justice in past when the Prosecutor and the Judge is the same person*

who sits on trial over the accused person. I would not go on stating details because it is very well known to the people as to why we have been advocating the separation of these two functions and it is absolutely necessary that these two functions should be separated."

H.V. Kamath supported the amendment moved by Prof. Shah, seeking to incorporate a new article, article 102-A, in the Constitution.

Alladi Krishnaswami Ayyar opposed the amendment on four grounds: first that it is not germane to the particular chapter: secondly, that it involves the exploring of the whole field of general administration: thirdly, that it is sure to put the whole administration out of gear: fourthly, the words 'wholly independent' and 'wholly separate' will lead of considerable difficulty.

B.R. Ambedkar told the House that he thinks no reply is necessary as the matter was discussed in great detail when they were discussing the Directive principle of State Policy and later the matter was practically concluded in article 39-A.

Thereafter, The motion was negatived.

This is how the two attempts regarding the incorporation of the Doctrine of Separation of Powers in the Indian Constitution failed.

Incorporation in the Constitution

At the first instance, it appears that our Constitution is based on this doctrine itself as the judiciary is self-sufficient and there is no interference either by executive or legislature. Constitution also prohibits the administration of judiciary not to be discussed in the parliament. The Legislature has also been entrusted with legislative powers and the Executive with its set of functions to be performed under the Constitutional Framework.

Constitutional Provisions that indicate a Separation of Functions are:

- Article 50 of the Constitution of India talks about the separation of the executive from the judiciary, as being a Directive Principle of State Policy it is not enforceable.
- Certain privileges, power, immunities are given to the Members of Parliament under Article 105. This provision makes the legislature independent.
- The executive power is conferred on President and Governor, while they are being exempted from civil and criminal liabilities.(Art.361)
- Articles 121 & 211 provide that the legislatures cannot discuss the conduct of a judge of the Supreme Court or High Court. They can do so only in case of impeachment.

Constitutional Provisions that indicate Functional Overlapping :

- It is clear that doctrine is not accepted in a rigid sense in the Constitution. The executive is a portion of the legislature and is accountable for its conduct to the legislature and also it derives its authority from the legislature.(Art.75)
- Ordinarily, all the legislative power is vested in the legislature but in certain circumstances, the president is empowered to exercise the legislative powers by issuing ordinances under Article 123 when the Parliament is not in session or making the rules when there is an emergency. Same Power is exercised by Governors in the State under Article 213.
- Sometimes, the President and Governors may also exercise judicial powers like pardoning power under Art.72 & Art.161.
- When a President is being impeached, both houses take active participation and finalize the charges.(Art.61)

- The Council of ministers on whose aid and advise, the President and Governor acts are elected members of the Parliament & Legislature. (Art.74)
- The Judges of Supreme Court are appointed by President in consultation with Chief Justice and other Judges of the Supreme Court.(Art.124)
- Judiciary also performs the administrative actions while formulating the regulations and giving guidance to the subordinate courts as well as performs legislative powers by framing the rules regulating their own procedure.

So, it is presumed from the provisions of the Constitution that India being a parliamentary form of government does not follow the absolute separation but there is an amalgamation of the powers where the connections between the different wings are inevitable and it can be drawn from the constitution itself. Every organ performs all types of functions in one or other form subject to the check and balance by other organs. All three organs are interdependent because India has a Parliamentary democracy. This does not mean that the Doctrine of Separation of Powers is not accepted in India, it has been accepted up to a certain extent.

JUDICIAL PRONOUNCEMENTS

1. In re Delhi Law Act case

Hon'ble Chief Justice Kania observed that, "Although in the Constitution of India there is no express separation of powers, it is clear that a legislature is created by the Constitution and detailed provisions are made for making that legislature pass laws. It implies that unless it can be gathered from other provisions of the Constitution, other bodies executive or judicial are not intended to discharge legislative functions."

2. Rai Sahib Ram Jawaya Kapoor v. State of Punjab

Hon'ble Chief Justice B.K. Mukherjea observed that, "The Indian Constitution has not indeed recognized the doctrine of separation of powers in its absolute rigidity but the functions of the different parts or branches of the Government have been sufficiently differentiated and consequently, it can be very well said that our Constitution does not contemplate assumption by one organ or part of the State of the functions that essentially belong to another."

3. Ram Krishna Dalmia v. Justice Tendolkar

Hon'ble Chief Justice S.R. Das opined that in the absence of specific provision for separation of powers in our Constitution, such as there is under the American Constitution, some such division of powers legislative, executive and judicial- is nevertheless implicit in our Constitution.

4. In Udai Ram Sharma v. Union of India

Supreme Court held that "The American doctrine of well-defined separation of legislative and judicial powers has no application to India."

5. Kesavananda Bharti v. State of Kerala

Hon'ble Chief Justice Sikri observed: "Separation of powers between the legislature, the executive and the judiciary is a part of the basic structure of the Constitution; this structure cannot be destroyed by any form of amendment."

6. Smt. Indira Nehru Gandhi v. Raj Narain

Hon'ble Justice Chandrachud observed: "The American Constitution provides for a rigid separation of governmental powers into three basic divisions the executive, legislative and judicial. It is essential principle of that Constitution that powers entrusted to one department should not be exercised by any other department. The Australian Constitution follows the same pattern of distribution of powers. Unlike these Constitutions, the Indian Constitution does not expressly vest the three kinds of power in three different organs of the State. But the principle of separation of powers is not a magic formula for keeping the three organs of the State within the strict confines of their functions."

Chief Justice AN Ray observed that in the Indian Constitution, there is a separation of powers in broad sense only. A rigid separation of powers as under the American Constitution or under the Australian Constitution does not apply to India. The Court further held that adjudication of a specific dispute is a judicial function which Parliament even acting under a constitutional amending power can't exercise.

7. *Asif Hameed v. State of Jammu and Kashmir*

The Supreme Court observed: "Although the doctrine of separation of powers has not been recognised under the Constitution in its absolute rigidity but the Constitution makers have meticulously defined the functions of various organs of the State. Legislature, executive and judiciary have to function within their own spheres demarcated under the Constitution. No organ can usurp the functions assigned to another. The Constitution trusts to the judgment of these organs to function and exercise their discretion by strictly following the procedure prescribed therein. The functioning of democracy depends upon the strength and independence of each of its organs."

8. *State of U.P. v. Jeet Singh Bisht*

Justice Markandey Katju commented that the judiciary must exercise self-restraint and refrain from entering into the domains of legislature and executive. Judicial Restraint protects the independence of Judiciary.

9. *Divisional Manager, Aravalli Golf Club v. Chander Hass*

The Supreme Court held that under the Constitution; the legislature, the executive and the judiciary all have their own broad spheres of operation. Ordinarily, it is not proper for any of these three organs of the state to encroach upon the domain of the other, otherwise, the delicate balance in the constitution will be upset and there will be a reaction. Judges must know their limits and must not try to ruin the government. They must have modesty and humility and not behave like emperors.

10. *Common Cause (A Regd. Society) v. Union of India and Ors. (11 April, 2008)*

Jt. Katju declared that the prayers made in the petition required legislative and administrative instructions, which could only be given by the legislature or the executive. The judiciary can't violate the entire legislative or administrative field. If such an instruction is issued, it will violate the principle of Separation of Powers.

11. *The University of Kerala v. Council of Principals for Colleges, Kerala*

The question of great constitutional importance which has risen was whether after getting the recommendations of some expert body by court order, the court itself can implement the said recommendations by passing a judicial order or whether the court can only send it to the legislature or its delegate to consider making a law for implementation of these recommendations.

Jt. Katju said that the interim order directing the implementation of the commission's recommendations is equivalent to legislation. According to him, this kind of action by the Court violates the broad decentralization of the constitution, so an organ should not infringe on the field of another.

Recent Case-Laws

1. ***Kantaru Rajeevaru v. Indian Young Lawyers Association (2019)***

Justice Indu Malhotra in the Sabrimala Verdict opined that Judges should not impose their personal views, morality or rationality with respect to the form of worship of a deity. She further observed that A pluralistic society and secular polity would reflect that the followers of various sects have the freedom to practise their faith in accordance with the tenets of their religion. It is irrelevant whether the practice is rational or logical. Notions of rationality cannot be invoked in matters of religion by courts.

2. ***Anuradha Bhasin v. Union of India (2020)***

The court stated that an order suspending internet services indefinitely is impermissible under the Temporary Suspension of Telecom Services (Public Emergency or Public Service) Rules, 2017. Supreme Court refused to restore 4G internet services in the Union Territory of Jammu and Kashmir (UT) and issued an order stating that the executive will make a decision on this matter. It was criticised on the ground that safeguarding the right to internet and profession by restoring the internet was the task best suited to Supreme Court but it failed to protect the same.

Checks & Balances

All three branches have “checks and balances” over each other to maintain the balance of power and not to exceed the constitutional limits. These Checks and Balances is a unique feature of the Constitutions where the Doctrine of Separation of Powers is followed. Few of the instances where the Indian Constitution lead to this are:

- President can set aside a law passed by the legislative organ or an advise given by the Union Council of Ministers when it is inconsistent with the Constitution of India.
- Even if the President accepts a law duly passed by the legislature, it can be struck down by the Supreme Court after a fair trial if it is against the Basic structure of the Constitution.
- President can be removed from office for Unconstitutional decisions after an impeachment trial conducted by the parliament.
- President can be removed by Supreme Court of India under Article 71(1) for electoral malpractice or on the grounds of losing eligibility for the position.
- Parliament can impeach Judges of Supreme Court and High Courts for their incompetence and mala fides. A higher bench of judges can set aside the incorrect judgements of a smaller bench of judges to uphold the Constitution.
- The judiciary has the power of judicial review over the actions of the executive and the legislature.
- Although the judiciary is independent, the judges are appointed by the executive.
- The legislature can also alter the basis of the judgment while adhering to the constitutional limitation.

CONCLUSION

For the smooth functioning of any government, cooperation and coordination among all three wings of the government is necessary. Professor Garner said that “this doctrine is impracticable as working principle of Government. It is difficult to divide the functions of each organ on an accurate basis”. After considering all the aspects of separation of power, it needs to be remembered that complete separation of power is possible neither in theory nor in practice.

Indian Constitution had not indeed recognized the doctrine of separation of powers in its absolute rigidity but the functions of different parts or branches of the Government have been sufficiently differentiated. The Indian Judiciary has tried to maintain the Separation of Powers between various functionaries through its judicial decisions as the Constitutional Intention but at many times it has failed to do so due to Judicial Activism practiced by excited Judges when they got engaged themselves in policy decisions like Linking of Rivers, Blanket ban on playing of Fire-Crackers, Singing of National Anthem in Cinema Halls, Lodha Committee on BCCI, etc. At the same time, it was expected of them to exercise some restraint and abide by the Separation of Powers intended by the Constitution.

If the legislature or the executive is not functioning properly it is for the people to correct the defects by exercising their franchise properly in the next elections and voting for candidates who will fulfil their expectations, or by other lawful methods like peaceful demonstrations. The remedy is not in the judiciary taking over the legislative or executive functions, because that will not only violate the delicate balance of power

enshrined in the Constitution, but also harm the institution of judiciary as it neither has the expertise nor the resources to perform those functions.

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